

Olojo Festival in Ile-Ife

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The Olojo ritual is an ancient spiritual observance undertaken annually by the people of Ile-Ife. The Olojo cult is associated with Ogun, the mythical figure and God of iron and smithery among the Yoruba people. He is regarded as a primordial deity who descended from the sky heaven at Ile-Ife to carry out the instructions of Olodumare (the supreme being), who had sent him to remold the earth and all that it contains. The Olojo festival is therefore associated with the "owner of the day" as the word Olojo can be loosely translated as the owner of the day or the creator of the day among the Yoruba. During this ritual, the king plays a central role. He goes into seclusion for the first seven days of the ritual. This is done with fasting and abstinence from sexual contact to ensure he is ritually pure to undertake the duties assigned to him during the annual ritual. The Iredumi and Osogun, who are directly connected to the Olojo ritual, also fast in anticipation of the ceremony so they are ritually prepared for the festival. The preparedness of the king and Olojo priests ensures a smooth ritual celebration. Ancestors are another unique participant in the ritual process. They are called upon, invoked, and asked to assume their ritual role and ensure the ritual is successful. The Olojo festival is a communal celebration, and it requires the active participation of men, women, and people of all ages. A lot of singing, chanting, drumming, rejoicing, and supplications are undertaken during the ritual. During the reign of the immediate past Oba of Ile-Ife, the festival was usually held in late October, but since the current Oba ascended the throne in 2014, the festival has now been held in the last week of September. The celebration is usually characterized by the influx of observers and participants from across the globe; while feasting and anticipation fill the air.

Date Range: 1500 CE - 2026 CE

Region: Ile-Ife

Region tags: Nigeria, Ile-Ife

Ile-Ife is the ancestral home of the Yoruba people

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Site

Does the ritual take place in an outside setting?

– Yes

↳ Enclosed?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual takes place at both inner and outer sacred spaces. Ooni, the king and one of the principal ritual personae, will be in seclusion for seven days inside the palace, communing with the deities and the past royal fathers, asking for blessings for his subjects.

↳ Elevated?

– Yes

Notes: The open ritual takes place in Oke-mogun, the sacred hill that was believed that Ogun landed when he arrived in Ile-Ife, the ancient home of the Yoruba people

↳ By a body of water?

– No

Notes: Ritual sacrifice during the Olojo celebrations do not take place near water bodies because the deity is not associated with water. However, other deities like Osun and Olokun are often receive their sacrifices by the water site or river site because they are water goddess or deities

↳ Near fire (e.g., volcano, lava, human-made fire)?

– No

Notes: No, Ogun is not a fire god or deity, even though he and his adherents use fire to make the implements that are identified with Ogun

↳ In a location considered holy?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual often takes place in front of the King's palace (Ooni's palace) at a tree overlooking the palace, which is about 200 meters from the palace. It is a sacred place that is enclosed specifically for the ritual purpose meant to commemorate Ogun.

↳ Other [Specify]

– Specify: The ritual space is mythically considered the site of the beginning, where Ogun venerated Olojo upon his arrival in Ile-Ife.

Does the ritual take place in an inside setting?

– No

Notes: The ritual is a public worship by the priests and the participants

Is the ritual carried out in a public place?

– No

Notes: The ritual personae allow for public participation; the only clause is that the sacred ritual place can only accommodate a few members of the public.

Is the ritual carried out in a private place?

– No

Notes: Apart from the pre-ritual stage, when only Ooni goes into seclusion, the ritual itself is a public spectacle

Is there a specific site or building associated with this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: There is an enclosed sacred space, but visible to the public.

Is the site associated with this ritual considered sacred?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual space is sacred, and every activity carried out in this place is sacred.

Was the site associated with this ritual created?

– Yes

↳ Was it temporary?

– No

Notes: The sacred space has been there since time immemorial. There is a sacred tree in the sacred space, which is believed by the worshippers and priests to be the place Ogun usually rested.

↳ Was it permanent?

– Yes

Notes: The sacred place is permanent and considered sacrosanct.

Was the site associated with this ritual found?

– Yes

↳ Through divination:

– Yes

Notes: It was through Ifa divination that the place was located and dedicated to the worship of Ogun (Olojo). There is a need to know that Ifa divination helps in knowing when and where Yoruba people can settle and take actions for further expansion

↳ Through astronomical observation:

– No

Notes: Oftentimes, Yoruba people use Ifa divination to know the mind of Olodumare and the deities or divinities

↳ Through myths, legends or literature:

– Yes

Notes: Myths of creation play crucial roles in the decisions that native people, especially the Yoruba people, make. Myths of the principal divinities or deities also play important role in this process. For example, there was a myth that was told to the people about the specific location where Ogun (Olojo) usually used as his resting place

Is the site associated with a metaphysical concept?

– Yes

Notes: The myth that established the site is both metaphysical and cosmological

Is the site representative of another physical or metaphysical space?

– Yes

Notes: All the Yoruba people, both at home and in diaspora, have ritual sites for Ogun called Olojo in Ile-Ife. Ogun shrines are present everywhere in the Yoruba villages and cities. It was believed that Ogun engaged in many peripatetic journeys, which makes it possible to have this site as a representative of another

physical space.

Is the site oriented to the sun, stars, or other astronomical features?

– No

Notes: The site does not have anything to do with the sun, moon, stars and other astronomical features. As said earlier, the location of the site is usually orchestrated through Ifa divination

Does the site have a particular directional orientation (e.g., N, S, E, W)?

– No

Notes: Apart from Ifa divination, most Yoruba palaces have Ogun shrines located at equidistant points from them. This ritual site is, however, located at a place further from the palace.

Is the site oriented to landforms (e.g., mountains, rivers, coast, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: Most Yoruba deities or divinities are believed to inhabit hills and mountains and other natural forces. The ritual site of the Olojo deity is called Oke (Hill), which is equivalent to a mountain.

Frequency

How often is this ritual performed?

– Yes

↳ Annually:

– Yes

Notes: It used to take place in the last week of October of each year during the era of the late Ooni Okunade Sijuade, but in the current dispensation, the new king, Eniitan Ogunwusi has changed the ritual ceremony to last weekend in September and at times spill over to the first week in October of every year since 2014.

↳ Daily:

– No

Notes: With the exception that blacksmiths, drivers, and people who use iron implements may occasionally take personal initiative to perform individual rituals to worship Ogun. The collective

ritual, however, takes place once a year.

↳ Weekly:

– No

Notes: This follows the immediate answer above

↳ Seasonally:

– Yes

Notes: It is done very close to the time, raining season is about winding up.

↳ Once in an individual's lifetime:

– No

Notes: It is an annual event

↳ Special events/occasions:

– Yes

Notes: Individuals can decide to carry out the rituals to commemorate important milestones in their lives namely, purchasing a new car or vehicle, concluding blacksmith's apprentice and others. The communal Olojo ritual is, however, observed to commemorate Ogun's worship annually with elaborate ritual ceremonies to the deities associated with the event.

↳ During life cycle events (marriage, birth, death, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: It is a commemorative and performative ritual

– Yes

Notes: The ritual can be done to honour a deceased chief priest of Ogun and other important priests connected to Ogun worship

↳ Ad hoc:

– No

Notes: It is never carried out under any impulse or frivolously

Is the duration of the ritual unspecified?

– No

Notes: The duration of the ritual is specified as mentioned above, and it lasts about two weeks, leading to another important ritual festival

Is the duration of the ritual specified? (If so, include the range of duration in hours)

– Yes: 14

Notes: The ritual festival runs for fourteen days. The first seven days are meant for Ooni to be in seclusion and the last seven days for the public ritual performance of Olojo or Ogun

Participants

Are there agent(s) involved in this ritual?

def: this includes the enactor(s) of the ritual and/or entity or entities responsible for the efficacy of the ritual

– Yes

↳ How many agents are involved in this ritual?

– Yes: 100

Notes: The major ritual personae are the king, Osogun, and Iredumi, but there are other chief priests whose activities are very visible during the ritual ceremony of Olojo festival. Women play crucial roles in this ritual

↳ Are agents of specific gender/sex for this ritual?

– No

Notes: Both males and females participate

↳ What is the age range of agents in this ritual?

– Specify: 16-80

Notes: Many Yoruba rituals involve teenagers, who are meant to perpetuate the ritual in the future

↳ Do agents have to have biological distinctiveness for this ritual?

(e.g., twin, born breach, albino, mental illness, hermaphrodite, blind, other disability)

– No

Notes: Yoruba consider certain categories of people unfit for important rituals, such as the Olojo ritual festival. The biologically deformed people, even though they are called Orisa people (Eni Orisa), are often excluded from participating in important rituals

↳ Do agents have to have a specific social role for this ritual?

(e.g., widow, unmarried, etc.)

– Yes

Notes: Some of the agents also play political roles in society, since they are kings in their own right; hence, they are called Oba. Politicians also participate actively. It needs to be mentioned that Olojo festival has become a civil religion sort of.

↳ Are agents required to be insiders for this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are agents initiated?

– Yes

Notes: They must be initiated into the roles of ritual personae/chiefs. Every ritual performance in Yoruba land has a specific ritual person handling it. So, there are specialised ritual roles people play

↳ Are agents part of the social group?

– Yes

Notes: Most of the priests connected to this ritual are now upgraded to royal or kings overseeing people in their various domains and playing social and administrative roles. They also play political roles and see to the development of Ile-Ife city

↳ Other:

–Specify: They play the role of local judges too.

↳ Are agents required to be outsiders for this ritual?

– No

Notes: They are usually initiated and grow into becoming these agents

↳ Are agents required to be specialists for this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: They are ritual specialists who play specific roles by ensuring the correctness of the ritual and dynamic of collective rites.

↳ Are agents non-specialists for this ritual?

– No

Notes: Non-specialists are non-initiates, hence they are called ogberi (uninitiated)

↳ Are there specific prohibitions for agents in this ritual?

(e.g., menstruating women, men of a certain age)

– Marriage status: They are permitted to marry. In actual fact women in the households of the priests actively participate in the public form of ceremonial rituals and collective rites

– Age: Marriage age (20 and above) and 80 years

– Gender: Both males and females participate and play crucial roles in the ritual ceremony

– Social caste: They are either from chiefly or royal lineages

– Religious affiliation or status: Yoruba Indigenous religious tradition but in certain cases some of the priests combine either Islamic or Christian faith with this religious practice (syncretism)

– Physical state (e.g. menstruation, illness): Menstruating women are generally not permitted to enter shrines or approach the Orisa (deities) during this sacred period. The ritual involves intense purification rites

↳ Are there supernatural agents associated with this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are they deceased humans:

– Yes

↳ Are they ancestors:

– Yes

Notes: Ancestors' spirits are usually invoked during collective rituals such as the Olojo ritual festival.

↳ Are they non-human, organic entities:

– Yes

Notes: They are non-human animals that are necessarily part of the ritual

↳ Are they animals:

– Yes

Notes: Animals are part of the ritual

↳ Are they plants:

– Yes

Notes: Plants are part and parcel of the ritual,

↳ Other:

– Specify: Invisible spirits and unseen forces are usually conjured. According to Yoruba tradition and belief, invisible spirits and ancestors are absolutely present during the ritual celebration.

↳ Are they abiotic or inorganic entities:

– No

↳ Are they divine/spiritual beings:

– Yes

↳ Are they high gods:

– Yes

Notes: Ogun, who is worshipped during the Olojo ritual festival, was one of the principal deities believed to be sent by Olodumare from the heavenly realm of existence to the earthly realm.

↳ Are they mixed divine (high-god)/human beings:

– Yes

Notes: Ogun, as one of the Orisas (principal deities) was considered to be a divine-human being.

↳ Are they transformed/self-cultivated humans:

Definition: humans who have undergone deliberate efforts to change/refine/develop/transform themselves.

– No

↳ Other:

– N/A

Are there patient(s) involved in this ritual?

Definition: recipient, beneficiary, client, target, victim of ritual

– Yes

↳ Is the patient the same as the agent of the ritual?

– No

Notes: Apart from agents of ritual, it involves thousands of people, including residents, worshippers, and tourists, who gather to witness the Ooni of Ife emerge from seclusion and receive his blessings.

↳ Is the patient absent from the ritual?

– No

Notes: Patients are not usually absent during the rituals. They are expected to show commitment to the Orisa (Olojo in this case) by being present and pronounce their allegiance to them in order for the deity to also show commitment to them by providing solution to their challenges.

↳ Is the patient present during the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is the patient physically present?

– Yes

↳ Is the patient virtually present?

– Yes

Notes: People can participate virtually

↳ How many patients are required for the ritual to take place?

– Yes: 3000

↳ Do patients have to be of a specific gender/sex for the purpose of this ritual?

– No

Notes: Both males and females may be present for this ritual.

↳ What is the age range of patients in this ritual?

– Specify: 15-80

↳ Do patients have to have a specific social role for this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: They participate in cheering and praying as the King carries the ancient crown called Aare, praying for the people.

↳ Are patients required to be insiders for this ritual?

– No

Notes: They can be insider and outsider

↳ Are patients required to be outsiders for this ritual?

– No

Notes: Not necessarily, they can be both insiders and outsiders

↳ Are patients required to be specialists for this ritual?

– No

Notes: They can either be the audience or the spectators

↳ Are patients non-specialists for this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: They are just participants

↳ Are there specific prohibitions for patients in this ritual?

– Yes [specify]: They have restricted areas they can stand or sit to avoid ritual transgression

↳ Are there supernatural beings that act as patients in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are they deceased humans:

– Yes

↳ Are they ancestors:

– Yes

Notes: Ancestors are a necessary part of this ritual. Without their attendance at the ritual, prayers offered would not be considered answered.

↳ Are they non-human, organic entities:

– Yes

↳ Are they animals:

– Yes

↳ Are they plants:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– Specify: There is a general belief that during the ritual performance both human entities and non-human entities are usually present to serve as both observers and participants

Notes: For example, the ancestors' spirits are often invoked. Most especially, the spirits of the departed kings are usually invoked during this period

↳ Are they abiotic or inorganic entities:

– No

Notes: Abiotic or inorganic entities are not considered part of this ritual.

↳ Are they divine/spiritual beings

– Yes

↳ Are they high gods:

– Yes

↳ Are they mixed divine (high-god)/human beings:

– Yes

↳ Are they transformed/self-cultivated humans:

– Yes

↳ Others:

– No

– Yes

↳ Is the patient the same as the agent of the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The agent of ritual could serve as both agent and patient

↳ Is the patient absent from the ritual?

– No

Notes: He or she is normally present

↳ Is the patient present during the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is the patient physically present?

– Yes

↳ Is the patient virtually present?

– Yes

Notes: If it becomes impossible for patients to be physically present, they could join virtually or their spirits could be tuned to the celebration in the hope that their desires for longing to take part in the ritual would be met.

↳ How many patients are required for the ritual to take place?

– Yes: 100

Notes: The patients consist of the ritual personae or specialists directly connected to the ritual

↳ Do patients have to be of a specific gender/sex for the purpose of this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are they male:

– Yes

Notes: Most of the time

↳ Are they female:

– Yes

Notes: Females also play crucial roles as poets and praise-singers

↳ Are they transgender:

– I Don't Know

↳ Are they non-binary:

– I Don't Know

↳ Are they other:

– No

↳ What is the age range of patients in this ritual?

– Specify: Between 20-80 years

↳ Do patients have to have a specific social role for this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The King is one of the most important ritual specialists, followed by Osogun, the main ritualist or chief priest who performs the major role of oblation and sacrifice. The Araba Agbaye, Elesije, and Iyalorishas also play important roles in overseeing the king's seven-day seclusion.

↳ Are patients required to be insiders for this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Naturally, patients are required to be insiders for the ritual.

↳ Are patients required to be outsiders for this ritual?

– No

Notes: Although outsiders are permitted to observe the ritual and to join the crowd in commemorating the ritual celebration, significant actions and observances taken by initiates in respect of the ritual calls for those who are familiar with the ritual to be involved.

↳ Are patients required to be specialists for this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: They are the performers, without whom the ritual will not be acceptable.

↳ Are patients non-specialists for this ritual?

– No

↳ Are there specific prohibitions for patients in this ritual?

– Yes [specify]: The King must go into seclusion for seven days and engages in fasting. The other ritual specialists are to abstain from sexual and romantic activities before and during the festival

↳ Are there supernatural beings that act as patients in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are they deceased humans:

– Yes

Notes: Deceased humans who are otherwise called ancestors are a significant part of this ritual.

↳ Are they ancestors:

– Yes

Notes: Deceased humans who are otherwise called ancestors are a significant part of this ritual.

↳ Are they non-human, organic entities:

– Yes

↳ Are they animals:

– Yes

Notes: Animals are needed for sacrifice

↳ Are they plants:

– Yes

Notes: Special Plants are needed for the ritual performance

↳ Other:

–Specify: Certain Spirits that are non visible to the eyes are also conjured

↳ Are they abiotic or inorganic entities:

– Yes

↳ Are they rocks and stones:

– Yes

Notes: The ritual takes place on a hilly or rocky place. Rain often falls every year during the ritual performance

↳ Are they human-created objects:

– No

Notes: Those objects are believed to be divine or supernaturally orchestrated

↳ Are they landscape features:

– Yes [specify]: The ritual space is hilly under a big tree meant for the purpose of the ritual performance

↳ Are they divine/spiritual beings

– Yes

↳ Are they high gods:

– Yes

Notes: Ogun and other gods (deities) associated with Olojo ritual festival are invoked and are expected to be present

↳ Are they mixed divine (high-god)/human beings:

– Yes

Notes: They were once considered divine and then humans and back to the divine

↳ Are they transformed/self-cultivated humans:

– Yes

Notes: These groups of people are usually present too. For example, researchers and

scholars whose fields of study are directly connected with the ritual are often present

↳ Others:

– Yes [specify]: Politicians, technocrats and elites from all walks of life are often present to witness the ritual occasion

Are there participants other than the agent involved in this ritual?

Definition: besides the agent, other actively participating in ritual, by responding, singing, dancing, interacting with ritual agents

– Yes

↳ How many participants are involved in this ritual?

– Specify: More than 2000

↳ The participants' gender/sex is:

– Yes

↳ Male:

– Yes

Notes: A larger percentage of participants at the ritual are males

↳ Female:

– Yes

Notes: Females do participate at the ritual. They have specific roles they play during the ritual.

↳ Transgender:

– Yes

↳ Non-binary:

– I Don't Know

↳ Other:

–Specify: Many people participate that one may not be able to know their specific genders

↳ What is the age range of participants in this ritual?

–Specify: 13-80

↳ Do participants have a specific social role for this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Hailing, cheering, dancing, chanting, singing, drumming, and so on

↳ Are participants required to be insiders for this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Ritual Participants are the initiates and the people who belong to the ritual priestly families

↳ Are participants required to be outsiders for this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Some participants can be present who are not directly linked to the family of ritual performers

↳ Are participants required to be specialists for this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Those participants who are directly linked with the ritual processes are required to be specialists.

↳ Are participants non-specialists for this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: They could be, many people come to participate and watch how the ritual is being performed

↳ Are there specific prohibitions for participants to take part in this ritual?

–Yes [specify]: People are forbidden to enter restricted sacred or ritual space especially if they are

non-initiates

↳ Are there supernatural beings that act as participants in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are they deceased humans:

– Yes

Notes: Ancestors are an integral part of this ritual.

↳ Are they ancestors:

– Yes

Notes: Ancestors are integral participants in this ritual. Their presence is required for a successful ritual observance.

↳ Are they non-human, organic entities:

– Yes

↳ Are they animals:

– Yes

Notes: Since animals such as dogs and chickens are used, they equally participate in the ritual

↳ Are they plants:

– Yes

Notes: Palm fronds are used to delineate and demarcate the ritual space during the Olojo festival

↳ Other:

– Specify: Non-visible spirit beings are believed to be present like witches, wizards, sorcerers, and disembodied spirits

↳ Are they abiotic or inorganic entities:

– No

↳ Are they divine/spiritual beings

– Yes

Notes: Divine/spiritual beings are essential living components which must be present for the ritual to be successful.

↳ Are they high gods:

– Yes

↳ Are they mixed divine (high-god)/human beings:

– Yes

Notes: Ogun and other deities or the principal divinities are considered mixed divine (high-god) and human beings

↳ Are they transformed/self-cultivated humans:

– Yes

↳ Others:

– Yes [specify]: Spirit of the forests and the air are believed to be among the participants

Are there spectators in this ritual?

Definition: not actively participating in ritual or required to perform any actions

– Yes

↳ How many spectators observe this ritual?

– Yes: 3000

↳ The spectators' gender/sex is:

– Yes

↳ Male:
– Yes

↳ Female:
– Yes

↳ Transgender:
– Yes

↳ Non-binary:
– I Don't Know

↳ Other:
– Specify: Non-human entities are believed to participate

↳ What is the age range of spectators in this ritual?
– Specify: 10-80 years

↳ Do spectators have a specific social role for this ritual?
– Yes
Notes: Cheering, singing, dancing and praying

↳ Are spectators required to be insiders for this ritual?
– No

↳ Are spectators required to be outsiders for this ritual?
– Yes
Notes: Most spectators are usually outsiders

↳ Are spectators required to be specialists for this ritual?

– No

Notes: They do not have to be specialists

↳ Are spectators non-specialists for this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: In most cases, they are non-specialists

↳ Are there specific prohibitions for spectators to take part in this ritual?

– Yes [specify]: They must respect ritual boundaries and must not cross the lines

↳ Are there supernatural beings that act as spectators in this ritual?

– No

Notes: Supernatural beings are expected to aid the ritual by actively participating and helping human beings achieve their ritual goals

Cause/Trigger

Is this ritual practiced at will?

– No

Notes: The ritual is practised at an appointed time annually. It is not left to the discretion of anyone to simply decide at random whenever it suits them to hold the ritual. It is usually agreed upon and planned for making it predictable and ensuring the certainty of the performance.

Is participation obligatory?

– No

Is this ritual practiced as part of an event?

– Yes

Notes: It is annual commemoration of the Ogun festival known as Olojo festival

Is this ritual practiced as part of calendric or astrological causes/events?

– Yes

Is this ritual triggered by hemerological considerations (system of favorable/unfavorable days)?

– Yes

Notes: Chief Eredumi is one of the ritual personae specifically tasked to seek the face of Olodumare to be able to know the dating of the ritual festival

Is the ritual practiced in response to seasonal change?

– No

Notes: It is a ritual that is practiced annually irrespective of seasonal change

Is the ritual practiced in response to specific natural events (e.g., drought, ecological death, etc.)?

– No

Is the ritual practiced in response to specific social events (e.g., death of a leader, etc.)?

– No

Is the ritual performed in reaction to an ominous event?

– No

Notes: It is an annual event and is observed to keep its significance in the life and experience of the entire people of Ile-Ife.

Is this ritual practiced during a specific life stage?

– No

Is this ritual part of another ritual?

– No

Is this ritual financially sponsored by non-participants?

– Yes

↳ By a government or ruling elite:

– Yes

Notes: Given the significance of the ritual to the cradle of the Yoruba race, the State government and other well meaning individuals commit financial resources and other logistical resources towards the successful hosting of the ritual.

↳ By NGOs:

Definition: NGO: Non-profit organization

– Yes

↳ By clans or families:

– Yes [specify]: The Royal family, the Ife traditional rulers and others

↳ By particular individuals:

– Yes

Notes: There are many individual donors for this ritual at both home and abroad

↳ Other:

– Specify: Tourists and researchers contribute financially to the success of the ritual festival

Purpose

Is the purpose of this ritual for maintenance?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual is meant to sanctify and cosmologize the Ife city and its environs. While its primary purpose is to celebrate the creation of the world and honor Ogun, the god of iron, it also includes "Iwode," a community cleansing rite dedicated to the spiritual maintenance and protection of the city. This Iwode is usually performed by the women from the Iredumi family, one of the important priests connected with the Olojo ritual festival. This cleansing rite begins at the entrance of the gate to the city and ends at the front of the Ooni's palace.

Is the purpose of the ritual to cause a change?

– Yes

↳ Is the change expected to be positive:

– Yes

Notes: The ritual is expected to bring about advancement, fruitfulness and plenty harvest

↳ Is the change expected to be negative:

– No

↳ Is the change expected to be neutral:

– No

Notes: The change is expected to be positive.

↳ Select the type of change:

– Political

– Legal

– Social

– Cultural

– Spiritual

– Ecological

What is the domain involved in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is it divine/spiritual:

– Yes

Notes: The ritual is divine/spiritual in nature. Activities carried out in the ritual are believed to possess the power to alter events in the physical realm of the existence of the Ile-Ife people

↳ Is it non-human organic entities (e.g., nature, animals, plants):

– Yes

↳ Is it abiotic/inorganic entities (and objects):

– No

↳ Is it ecological:

– Yes

↳ Is it transformed humans:

– Yes

Notes: The ritual is closely associated with and has to do with the ancestors of the Yoruba race.

↳ Is it for knowledge transmission (e.g., oral storytelling):

– Yes

Notes: The time of the ritual is an occasion for retelling past events which brings the young into an atmosphere to learn about the history of their forebears as it serves as an occasion for continuity of the experiences of the people.

↳ Other:

–Specify: It is meant to enhance shared experience and commemorative

Is there a specific goal(s) associated with this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is devotion a goal of the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Devotion is an important goal of the ritual. The people use the occasion to pledge their loyalty to the Olojo.

↳ For deceased humans:

– Yes

↳ For ancestors:

– Yes

Notes: Ancestors are indeed an indispensable part of the ritual celebration.

↳ For non-human, organic entities:

– No

↳ For abiotic or inorganic entities:

– No

Notes: Abiotic and inorganic entities are not considered a part of this ritual.

↳ For divine/spiritual beings:

– Yes

↳ Are they high gods:

– Yes

↳ Are they mixed divine (high-god)/human beings:

– Yes

Notes: Since the ancestors are a part of this ritual, as they were formally humans who have transcended this realm, they form a part of the mixed/human beings who make the ritual unique.

↳ For transformed/self-cultivated humans:

– No

↳ Other:

–Specify: Devotion is part of the emotional and spiritual driving force behind any ritual performance

Notes: Any ritual such as this brings people from all walks of life to worship in songs, dance, and praise and prayers

↳ Is creation of a cultural product a goal of this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Ritual and religion are cultural systems according to anthropologists such as Clifford Geertz

↳ Is propitiation a goal of this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is domestication of agents a goal?

Definition: temporary or permanent transformation of an inimical or indifferent target into something beneficial for practitioners.

– No

Notes: Agents can function anywhere anytime

↳ Is this ritual practiced to gain information?

– No

Notes: The ritual is practiced to serve as a recreation myth and remind people of who they are and where they are coming from.

↳ Is this ritual practiced for cosmic maintenance?

– Yes

Notes: Most rituals, including this one are for cosmic maintenance

↳ Is this ritual practiced for ecological maintenance and/or stewardship?

– Yes

↳ To increase felt connection with the more-than-human world:

– Yes

Notes: As a matter of fact, ecological ritualization plays an important role in this ritual

practice

↳ To acknowledge responsibility for environmental harm:

– Yes

↳ To channel shame into collective reparative action:

– Yes

Notes: During the ritual and in fact in the daily conversation of the priests and adherents of the Olojo, they lament the moral decadence of the present world and its attendant consequences blaming them on the evils of the human race. They therefore call for caution and collective reparative action to restore order and global peace.

↳ To try to influence a larger change in the community (e.g., environmental values, motivations, beliefs, emotions):

– Yes

↳ To evoke moral outrage (towards ecological injustice):

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced for self-transformation?

– Yes

↳ To become god-like:

– No

↳ To become immortal:

– No

↳ To achieve divine or superhuman attributes:

– No

↳ For salvation/liberation from the world:

– No

↳ For spiritual cleansing:

– Yes

Notes: The followers of the Olojo deity use the ritual performance to ask spiritual cleansing of the land and the individuals who inhabit the land.

↳ To achieve moral perfection:

– No

↳ For an initiation into a new status:

– No

↳ To achieve a change in mental state:

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced as a way to express gratitude to a god or other supernatural agents?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual is commemorative as well as appreciative

↳ Is this ritual performed for purification?

– Yes

↳ Is it physical:

– No

↳ Is it mental:

– No

↳ Is it emotional:

– No

↳ Other:

–Specify: it is repetitive and performative

↳ Is this ritual practiced for exorcism purposes?

– Yes

↳ For expelling spirits:

– Yes

Notes: The ritual is meant to expel evil spirits both from individuals tormented by them and for the evil spirits which may be occupying the land.

↳ For summoning spirits:

– Yes

Notes: It is also meant to invite good spirits that will contribute to the societal progress

↳ For gaining special knowledge from spirits:

– Yes

Notes: This ritual helps the participants to gain new knowledge from the gods

↳ For spiritual communication:

– Yes

Notes: The ritual serves as an occasion to commune with Ogun, the god of Iron

↳ Is this ritual practiced for health/healing purposes?

– Yes

↳ During a specific illness?

– No

↳ During an injury?

– No

↳ To improve fertility?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual priest uses the occasion to pray for fertility

↳ To achieve longevity?

– Yes

Notes: During the ritual performance, prayers are offered for the king and his household and for the land that no sudden or untimely death will be witnessed in the land.

↳ To support development/growth?

– Yes

↳ To achieve vitality?

– Yes

↳ To improve virility?

– Yes

↳ To achieve resurrection?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced to transmit information?

– Yes

↳ Is this ritual practiced to obtain luck (generic)?

– No

↳ Is this a naming ritual?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced to improve the community's modes of subsistence?

– Yes

↳ To increase the amount of rain for agricultural/horticultural productivity:

– Yes

↳ For crop success:

– Yes

↳ For livestock success:

– Yes

↳ For success in gathering:

– Yes

↳ For success in fishing:

– Yes

↳ For success in hunting:

– Yes

↳ For industrial productivity:

– Yes

↳ For success in commerce/mercantilism/market exchange:

– Yes

↳ Is this ritual practiced to induce harm?

– No

Notes: Harm is not a focus of this ritual. In fact, in the observance of the ritual some patients seek to find reprieve from harm suffered or sicknesses they have encountered.

↳ Is this ritual practiced for protection purposes?

– Yes

Notes: The list of issues the ritual is believed to solve in the private and communal lives of the people involved in the Olojo ritual is endless. They seek protection from sudden death, loss, death, misfortunes, business failure, failure on journeys and on their farms among others.

↳ Against spells/witchcraft:

– Yes

↳ To avoid illness:

– Yes

↳ To avoid injury:

– Yes

↳ For a safe pregnancy:

– Yes

↳ For children:

– Yes

↳ To avoid discovery:

– No

↳ Against weapons:

– No

↳ To avoid vices (temptation):

– Yes

↳ Is this ritual associated with warfare or ritual contests (e.g., stick ball games)?

– No

↳ Is this ritual associated with craft practices (e.g., weaving, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual is associated with blacksmithing

↳ Is this ritual associated with infanticide?

– No

↳ Is this ritual associated with gambling/games of chance?

– No

↳ Is this ritual associated with travel?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual ceremony is used to solicit and pray for safe travels for everyone

↳ Is this ritual associated with social relations?

– Yes

Notes: Social relations are both established and strengthened as people attend this ritual. People normally bond, sing together, dance together and walk through the whole ritual process having their faith and hope in the powers of the Olojo to heed their supplication and attend to their challenges.

↳ As part of a celebration:

– Yes

↳ For love:

– Yes

Notes: The ritual is to bring people together as one love family, especially people who are directly connected with it.

↳ For social coordination:

– Yes

Notes: The ritual is religious as well as social. It brings people from different social backgrounds, such as political, economic, educational and cultural backgrounds together

↳ To reduce social discord:

– Yes

Notes: The ritual is also aimed at promoting social cohesion, just like Emile Durkheim has said in his book *Elementary Forms of Religious Life*

↳ To maintain partner faithfulness:

– No

↳ To cause religious conversion:

– No

Notes: The ritual is never done for proselytisation purposes; it is for religious and social cohesion

↳ To obtain subjugation/control:

– No

Notes: It is preeminently a ritual, social, and cultural thing

↳ Is this ritual practiced to obtain wealth or success?

– Yes

↳ For professional success (e.g., exam, promotion):

– Yes

Notes: Prayers are offered for successes in all areas of endeavours

↳ For legal success:

– Yes

↳ To obtain income/wealth:

– Yes

Notes: Prayers are usually offered for riches and wealth

↳ To escape debt:

– Yes

Notes: People pray to the deity (Ogun: the god of Iron) to be free from debt

↳ For business success:

– Yes

Notes: Ritual priests pray for business success for all participants

↳ To recover lost objects:

– Yes

Notes: The ritual is also done to pray for the recovery of lost items and objects

↳ Other:

–Specify: During the ritual festival, prayers for preservation, protection and prevention of loss are usually offered for all participants

Is the causal efficacy assessed?

– Yes

↳ Concrete outcomes in the world:

– Yes

Notes: People give testimonies of answered prayers during the past year's ritual prayer performance in the subsequent years

↳ Further ritual checks:

– Yes

Notes: The ritual serves as a check against disasters, accidents, and calamities

↳ Other:

– Specify: The ritual is a time to ask for good harvest, peace and harmony in and out of the ritual domain that is, Ile-Ife and its environs

Notes: The Priests take time to pray for the King and chiefs, and the king also uses the occasion to pray for his subjects for progress and harmonious living.

Techniques

Is sound practiced during this ritual?

– Yes

Is it considered "music" in the local culture/community?

– Yes

Is this sound coordinated with movement?

– Yes

↳ Is it oral?

– Yes

↳ Is it communal? (e.g., choir)

– Yes

Notes: There are groups of women who sing during the ritual. Their songs occupy a

significant position in the ritual process.

↳ Is it individual?

– Yes

Notes: Individuals also sing during the ritual to the Olojo whom they have come to worship and adulate.

↳ Is there a call and response?

– Yes

↳ It involves singing:

– Yes

↳ It involves chanting:

– Yes

Notes: Chanting is an important part of the ritual. Priests chant in honour of the Ogun deity singing his praise and remembering his heroic acts. They do this to invoke his spirit and presence and to get the environment charged for spiritual/divine impartation.

↳ it involves invocation/prayer:

– Yes

↳ It involves mantras:

– No

↳ It involves wailing/cheering (heightened emotional expression):

– Yes

Notes: A lot of wailing, cheering and heightened emotional expressions take place during this ritual

↳ It involves narrative/recitation:

– Yes

↳ It involves whistling:

– Yes

↳ It involves shouting/loud vocalizations:

– Yes

↳ How many individuals are involved in creating the vocalizations?

– Yes

Notes: As many as a hundred or more people, especially women chanters from the Iredumi's family

↳ Is the sound scripted?

– No

Notes: Chants are not scripted. They are learned and committed to heart for recitation during every Olojo ritual.

↳ Is the sound semantic?

– No

↳ Is it mimetic (of non-human animal, natural, human)?

– Yes

↳ Is it restricted to ritual use?

– Yes

↳ Is it specifically carried out by ritual specialists?

– Yes

Notes: Women from the Iredumi family are experts in chants, songs and other recitations during this ritual.

↳ Does it require formal training?

– Yes

Notes: The vocalization is learnt by mimicking elderly ritualists

↳ Do the vocalizations change throughout the ritual?

– No

↳ Is there musical texture in the loud vocalizations?

– Yes

↳ Is it homophonic:

– Yes

Notes: Homophonic sounds form part of the sounds produced during the festival

↳ Is it monophonic:

– No

↳ Is it polyphonic:

– Yes

↳ Is it heterophonic:

– Yes

Notes: Both polyphonic and heterophonic sounds are made during the ritual. These see groups of worshippers sing together making beautiful loud vocalisation which adds colour to the ritual celebration

↳ Is it biphonic:

– Yes

↳ Are the vocalizations regulated by pitch?

– Yes

Notes: Vocalisations during the ritual performance are regulated by pitch

↳ Are they codified?

– Yes

↳ Are the vocalizations regulated by rhythm?

– Yes

↳ Do they have a pulse?

– Yes

↳ Do they involve codified patterns?

– Yes

↳ The pace of the rhythm is:

– Specify: fast

↳ Are the vocalizations considered central to the ritual?

– Yes

↳ The sound is:

– Improvised

↳ Is the sound produced with parts of the body?

– Yes

↳ Does the sound involve hand movement?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve clapping?

– Yes

Notes: Especially women from the Eredumi priestly family sing and clap their hands

↳ Does it involve body concussion?

– No

↳ Does the sound involve feet movement?

– Yes

↳ How many individuals are involved in producing the sound:

– Yes

Notes: As many as the participants, especially the ritual specialists and people from their family

↳ Is the sound/movement scripted?

– No

Notes: Sounds and movements are not scripted. They are done with joy and excitement.

↳ Is the sounds/movement semantic?

– No

Notes: Sounds and movements in this ritual are not semantic. They are oral, preserved, transmitted and have been efficacious for centuries.

↳ Is the sounds/movement mimetic (of non-human animal, natural, human)?

– Yes

Notes: The sounds and movement are patterned after the departed ancestors

↳ Is this sound/movement restricted to ritual use?

– Yes

Notes: Many of the sounds and movements in this ritual are restricted to ritual use and not to be uttered profanely without ritual purpose.

↳ Is the sound/movement carried out by specialists?

– Yes

↳ Does it require formal training?

– No

Notes: People learn by observation

↳ Does the sound/movement change throughout the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is the change correlated to the stage of the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Different stages of the ritual demand different song type and chant styles. The initiates who are involved know what to do at different times and stages of the ritual process.

↳ Is there musical texture in the sound?

– Yes

↳ Is it homophonic:

– Yes

↳ Is it monophonic:

– Yes

↳ Is it polyphonic:

– Yes

↳ Is it heterophonic:

– Yes

↳ Is it biphonic:

– No

Notes: The songs are sung at the same time by participants. They are started together and ended at the same time by individuals constituting the singing group.

↳ Is the sound regulated by pitch?

– Yes

↳ Is it codified?

– No

Notes: Sounds during the ritual are regulated by pitch but are not codified. They are passed down from generation to generation and transmitted in their oral form.

↳ Is the sound regulated by rhythm?

– Yes

↳ Is there a pulse?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve codified patterns?

– Yes

↳ The pace of the rhythm is:

– Yes

Notes: Fast and at times can be slow, depending on the type of song and rhythm

↳ Is the sound considered central to the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Sounds are a means of communicating in the course of the ritual. They are therefore central to the ritual process.

↳ The sound is:

– Improvised

↳ Does the sound involve conscious agency?

– Yes

↳ Are there instruments/objects involved in creating sounds for the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are they membranophone:

Definition: Instruments that produce sound by vibrating a membrane (e.g., kettle drums, cylindrical drums).

– Yes

Notes: Drums play an essential part in music and dancing during the ritual

↳ Are they idiophone:

Definition: Instruments that create sound through vibrating themselves (e.g., xylophones, jaw's harp).

– Yes

↳ Are they aerophone:

Definition: Instruments that create noise by pushing vibrating columns of air through them (e.g., accordions, pitch pipes, ocarinas, bagpipes).

– Yes

↳ Are they chordophone:

Definition: Instruments that produce sound by vibrating strings (e.g., guitar, violin, harp).

– No

Notes: No chorded instruments are deployed during the ritual festival.

→ Are they electrophone:

Definition: Instruments where the sound is produced by electric or electronic means (e.g., synthesizers, computers).

– No

Notes: No electrophone musical instruments are deployed during the ritual.

→ Are they architectural features:

def: water channeled in underground canals, fountains, or other architectural features that create sounds for the ritual

– No

→ How many individuals are involved in producing these instrumental sounds:

– Yes

Notes: More than 100 people

→ Is it scripted?

– No

→ Is it semantic?

– No

→ Is it mimetic (of non-human animal, natural, human)?

– Yes

Notes: The music and sound are believed to be mimetic of past ancestors

→ Is it restricted to ritual use?

– Yes

- ↳ Is it performed by specialists?
 - Yes

- ↳ Does it require formal training?
 - Yes

- ↳ Does the sound change throughout the ritual?
 - No

- ↳ Is there musical texture in the instrumental sound?
 - Yes

 - ↳ Is it homophonic:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Is it monophonic:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Is it polyphonic:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Is it heterophonic:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Is it biphonic:
 - No

- ↳ Is the sound regulated by pitch?
 - Yes

↳ Does it involve codified patterns?

– Yes

↳ Is the sound regulated by rhythm?

– Yes

↳ Is there a pulse?

– Yes

↳ Codified/non-codified patterns

– Yes

↳ The pace of the rhythm is:

– Yes

Notes: fast and can be slow at times

↳ Is the sound considered central to the ritual?

– Yes

↳ The sound is:

– Improvised

Is movement involved in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is it considered "dance" by the culture that practices this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is it coordinated with sound?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve the use of objects?

– Yes

↳ How many individuals are involved in this movement

– Specify: Ritual personae

↳ Do actors move in close proximity to each other?

– Yes

↳ Do actors move towards each other?

– Yes

Notes: Actors in the ritual do move towards each other. They congregate together and operate as a formidable unit to ensure the ritual is successful.

↳ Do actors move away from each other?

– No

↳ Does it involve ritualized action?

– Yes

↳ It involves kneeling:

– Yes

Notes: There times when the ritual performers kneel, bow their heads, fall on their faces and perform other actions necessary for ritual acceptance.

↳ It involves prostrating:

– Yes

↳ Does it involve remaining immobile:

– Yes

Notes: Sometime before the ritual personalities begin to move again

↳ Does it involve artistic movement (e.g., mandala)?

– Yes

↳ Is it mimetic (natural, non-human world)?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve a symbolic representation?

– Yes

↳ Does it include stereotyped/stylized movements?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve a procession?

– Yes

↳ Is the procession one way?

– Yes

Notes: From the king's palace to the sacred grove of Ogun tree

↳ Is the procession multidirectional?

– No

↳ Is the procession a roundtrip?

– Yes

Notes: The procession which moves from the king's palace to the ritual site also returns with the king at the conclusion of the ritual. They process with anticipation but return with excitement and fulfillment.

↳ Does it involve a pilgrimage?

– Yes

↳ What is the distance covered (in kilometers)?

– Specify: 0.5

↳ Are there gestures involved in the movement?

– Yes

Notes: There are ritual gestures of facial, tactile and bodily movements

↳ Are there particular postures involved in the movement?

– Yes

↳ Is it choreographed?

– Yes

Notes: Songs rendered during the ritual are often choreographed.

↳ Is it a narrative?

– Yes

↳ Is it restricted to the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is it involuntary? (caused by trance, etc.)

– No

↳ Is there a specific proximity considered between individuals while moving?

– Yes

↳ Are individuals close to one another?

– Yes

↳ Is there physical contact between individuals?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve touch?

– Yes

Notes: Physical contact between participants often involve touch

↳ Does it involve holding hands?

– Yes

Notes: There are times when participants hold hands as mark of solidarity and unity in the performance of the ritual.

↳ Does it involve linking arms?

– Yes

Notes: The atmosphere during the ritual is usually demonstrative of love and unity. This is manifested sometimes as participants hold hands and link arms while performing the ritual.

↳ Does it involve embracing?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve kissing?

– No

↳ Does it involve sexual contact?

– No

Is there regalia/ornamentation used as part of this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are there specific body markings done for the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Body markings done for the purpose of the ritual are temporary. They get cleaned off after the ritual performance.

↳ Are they permanent:
– No

↳ Are they temporary:
– Yes

↳ Is there hair regulation as part of this ritual?
– Yes

↳ Does it involve shaving:
– Yes

Notes: Some votaries of the Olojo do shave their hair before the ritual. They do this as part of their dedication and ritual cleansing before the ritual gets underway.

↳ Does it involve a specific hair style:
– Yes

↳ Is there tooth modification involved in this ritual?
– No

Notes: Tooth modification are not a part of this ritual

↳ Are individuals partly or fully naked as part of this ritual?
– No

↳ Are scars made as part of this ritual?
– No

↳ Are piercings made as part of this ritual?

– No

Notes: No body scarring or piercings are done during this ritual.

↳ Does genital modification take place during this ritual?

– No

↳ Do individuals have to wear specific clothing for this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are there specific shoes to be worn for this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is there a head covering used during the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The king who is one significant ritual actor in this ritual wears the Aare crown. It is believed to be an ancestral crown which is very heavy. It has a ritual significance in the celebration. Women also wear head gears while participating in the ritual.

↳ Is it removed at some point during the ritual?

– No

↳ Is it added during the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are the clothing colors regulated for the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are there specific clothing items restricted for exclusive use in the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Body revealing clothes are not customarily worn during the ritual. Clothing should be decent and cover private areas of the body.

↳ Are there jewelry/charms used during this ritual?
– Yes

↳ Are masks used during the ritual?
– No

Are there materials/objects used in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are they totems:
– Yes

↳ Are they religious icons:
– Yes

Notes: Various icons of spiritual significance are used by the Olojo priests to ensure the sanctity of the ritual.

↳ Are they fetishes:
– Yes

↳ Are they vessels:
– Yes

Notes: Vessels are used to convey sacrificial items and other ritual necessities to the ritual site by designated votaries of the Olojo deity.

↳ Are they masks:
– No

↳ Are they standards (banner, flag):

– Yes

↳ Other:

– Specify: Three important ritual personae namely the Ooni, Chief Osogun and Chief Eredumi must wear crown that is veiled

↳ How are these materials/objects implemented?

– Yes

↳ Are they sound-producing:

– Yes

↳ Are they divination tools:

– Yes

↳ Are they drug paraphernalia:

– Yes

↳ Are they cutting devices:

– Yes

Notes: Cutting devices and sharp tools like knives are used to perform sacrifices during the ritual.

↳ Are they sceptres/wands:

– Yes

↳ Is text used during this ritual?

– No

Notes: Texts are not used during the ritual

↳ Is painting used during the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The Oke Mogun shrine and other ritually important places are often painted before the ritual celebration. This adds colour to the occasion and brings out the beautiful and captivating scene of the ritual site.

↳ Is a technological object used in this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual has been greatly modernized with a lot of electronic billboards, Public address systems, televised ritual, and so on.

↳ Are plants or plant parts used in this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: A lot of ritually potent leaves are used during the ritual. Palm fronds are also used to demarcate the ritual site to maintain ritual boundary for the purpose of maintaining the purity of the ritual site.

↳ Are animals or animal parts used in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are human body parts (including flesh) used in this ritual?

– No

↳ Are bodily fluids used as part of this ritual?

– No

↳ Do topical applications take place during this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is water used?

– Yes

Notes: Water is symbolic in Yoruba cosmology. It is used to ritual purposes during the ritual.

↳ Is earth used?

– Yes

↳ Is a mirror used?

– No

↳ Are textiles used?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual participants and their families are usually robed in a specialised textile

↳ Is fire used?

– No

↳ Is there interaction with ritual material during the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: There is a lot of interaction with ritual items during the ritual. Some are touched, used to touch other items, placed at specific ritually significant places during the ritual or used to mark ritual boundaries.

↳ Is it passed around?

– No

↳ Is it kissed?

– No

↳ Is it placed somewhere specifically?

– Yes

↳ Is it processed to create something else?

– No

↳ Is it touched?

– Yes

↳ Is it used to touch?

– Yes

↳ Is it altered during the course of the ritual?

– No

↳ Is it worn?

– Yes

↳ Is it used to maintain a boundary?

– Yes

↳ Is it placed at a specific physical distance?

– Yes

↳ Is it close?

– Yes

↳ Is it far?

– No

Does consumption take place as part of this ritual?

– Yes

↳ How many individuals participate in consumption?

– Specify: 500

↳ Is food consumed?

– Yes

↳ Is it human:

Definition: this can include by fire, natural features of landscape

– No

Notes: No human part is consumed before, during or shortly after this ritual.

↳ Is it a non-human animal:

– Yes

Notes: Animals are consumed during and after the ritual.

↳ Is it a plant:

– Yes

↳ Is it a fungus:

– No

↳ Is this food restricted to the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is the preparation of the food ritualized?

– Yes

Notes: Foods prepared for the purpose of the ritual have to be made following strict procedures to ensure they meet the requirements of the ritual and to ensure ritual compliance.

↳ Is the presentation of the food ritualized?

– Yes

↳ In what state is the food consumed?

– Cooked

↳ Is a non-normative portion (excessive or deficient) served?

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes a small portion of ritually charged foods are consumed by designated actors/participants in the ritual

↳ Is it sacralized food?

– Yes

↳ Is it symbolic food?

e.g., standing in for another food or substance or metaphysical concept

– Yes

↳ Is the food consumed associated with healing powers?

– Yes

Notes: Since some of the food consumed during the ritual are ritually charged or incubated, they are viewed as possessing special powers which could cause healing, bring comfort or sooth those who consume the food.

↳ Does food consumption happen on site?

– Yes

↳ Does the food consumption happen off site?

– Yes

↳ Does the ritual take place before food consumption?

– No

Notes: The food consumption can happen before or after ritual

↳ Are there specific types of consumption that are forbidden?

– Yes

Notes: Each Orisa (deity) has specific food items that must be consumed during ritual festivals, just as each of them has its own food taboos.

↳ Is a psychoactive substance used in this ritual?

– No

↳ How is the substance used in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is it smoked:

– No

↳ Is it ingested:

– Yes

↳ Alone:

– No

↳ With food:

– Yes

↳ With liquid:

– Yes [specify]: A powder substance prepared as charm can be consumed with liquid such as liquor

↳ Is it applied topically:

– Yes

↳ Is it chewed:

– Yes

↳ Is it a suppository:

– No

↳ Is it snorted:

– No

↳ Is it injected:

– No

↳ Is it offered into the fire:

– Yes

Notes: Since the ancestors are present during the ritual, libations are poured out to them and some of the items are also thrown into the fire as ritual substances to the deity.

↳ Is it offered to non-human animals or natural features:

– Yes

↳ Does it require fasting beforehand:

– Yes

Notes: The king and the head of the Olojo ritual cult undertake fasting before the ritual. This is to prepare them for the ritual and to ensure all things are taken care of spiritually before the ritual takes place.

↳ Does it cause vomiting:

– No

↳ Are other substances used in this ritual?

– I Don't Know

↳ Is the substance shared from a communal vessel or implement?

– Yes

Does the ritual stimulate an altered state of consciousness?

– No

Are offerings involved as part of this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are the offerings non-material?

– Yes

↳ Are the offerings material?

– Yes

↳ Are they consumed by the ritual participants?

– Yes

Notes: Ritual participants consume some of the offerings made during the ritual.

↳ Are the offerings symbolic?

– Yes

Notes: The offerings presented during the ritual are symbolic in the sense that they have specific purposes they serve towards the success of the ritual. Either they are foods, animals or other objects, they have specific purposes they serve in the ritual process.

↳ Is there a substitution used to represent the symbolic offerings?

– Yes

Notes: Rolling on the ground and praising the deity

↳ Do offerings serve as payments for the ritual specialists?

– Yes

↳ Are animals offered?

– Yes

↳ Is the whole animal offered?

– Yes

↳ How many animals are offered?

– Specify: 2

↳ Is part of the animal offered?

– No

↳ Are the animals domestic?

– Yes

↳ How many domestic?

– Specify: 2

↳ Are they wild animals?

– No

↳ Are humans offered?

– No

Notes: Humans are not offered during the ritual

↳ Is food offered for this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Foods which are ritually acceptable to the Olojo deity are offered during the ritual.

↳ Are specific drinks offered for this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are psychoactive substances offered?

– No

↳ Are commodities offered?

– No

↳ Are household items offered?

– Yes

↳ Are personal items offered?

– Yes

↳ Is clothing offered?

– No

↳ Are musical instrument offered?

– No

↳ Are texts offered?

– No

↳ Are weapons offered?

– Yes

↳ Is money (or other valuable items) offered?

– Yes

↳ Are precious substances offered?

– Yes

Notes: Several items including animals, commodities, valuables etc are offered during the ritual.

↳ Other:

– N/A

Are non-normative practices involved in this ritual?

– No

Formal Features

Does the ritual stand by itself?

– Yes

Is the ritual part of a sequence of rituals?

– No

Notes: The ritual is a major celebration among the Ile-Ife people. It is a significant annual celebration which is associated with the Olojo (Ogun worshippers) in the city.

Is the repetition of the ritual determinate (e.g., an action must be repeated a certain number of times)?

– Yes

Is the repetition of the ritual non-determinate?

– No

Compared to everyday non-ritual behavior, what is the level of repetition?

– High

Compared to everyday non-ritual behavior, what is the level of rigidity of this ritual?

– High

Compared to everyday non-ritual activity, what is the level of arousal of this ritual?

– High

Compared to everyday non-ritual activity, what is the level of physical activity in this ritual?

– High

Is there behavioral conformity?

– Yes

↳ What is the level of behavioral conformity
– High

Is there synchrony in this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Certain actions are required of the ritual performers in certain sequence, order and manners for a smooth and acceptable ritual process.

↳ Are the roles differentiated?
– Yes

Is there entrainment in this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual process involves a lot of synchrony of dancing, chanting, movement etc. Participants know the importance of this and do act in manners acceptable for the success of the ritual.

↳ What is the level of entrainment?
– High

↳ Is there movement/sound/attention?
– Yes

↳ Is the entrainment emerging endogenously between participants in the ritual?

(e.g., clapping, chanting without external stimulus)

– Yes

↳ Is the entrainment to an external stimulus?

(e.g., a ritual leader, a musical beat)

– Yes

↳ Does the entrainment induce emotional conformity?

– Yes

Is there coordination in this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Coordination of the ritual is highly organised. The heads of the Olojo cult ensure individuals saddled with responsibilities are competent and a high level of expectation is placed on those who are saddled with every little or great duty to ensure ritual effectiveness.

↳ What is the level of coordination?

– High

↳ Is there movement/sound/attention?

– Yes

Is there preparation time needed to carry out this ritual?

– Yes

How many hours are involved in the ritual preparation?

– Specify: 86

Are there preparation activities involved?

– Yes

Notes: A lot of preparation is taken into account to ensure a successful Olojo ritual celebration. The king fasts, abstains from sexual intercourse for the first one week of the celebration while others also are expected to be ritually pure, take part in penance and other ritual activities required to have a successful ritual celebration.

↳ Does it involve fasting:
– Yes

↳ Does it involve purification:
– Yes

↳ Does it involve learning/training:
– Yes

↳ Does it involve penance:
– Yes

↳ Does it involve abstention:
– Yes [specify]: Fasting and abstinence from sexual activity for 7 days especially by the Ooni (the King)

Is practice/expertise required to carry out this ritual?

– Yes

What is the level of expertise required?

– High

What is the level of economic cost involved to practice this ritual?

– Yes

↳ In local currency:

– Specify: Millions of Naira

↳ Number of people or days of labor equivalent:

– Specify: More than two hundred people and at least a month of labor in preparation for this ritual

↳ Other measure of cost:

– Specify: Miscellaneous spending

What is the transmission mode of the ritual?

- Vertical
- Horizontal
- Esoteric

How is the ritual transmitted?

- In oral form
- Artistic representation
- Through inspiration
- Through social imitation

Who or what has authority over this ritual?

- Divine beings
- Myth or legend
- Sagely human
- Religious specialists
- Other:: The King and the two important ritual chiefs (Iredumi and Osogun) are usually people that wield authority over this ritual

Bibliography

General References

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